

FORMATION OF INFORMATION-COMMUNICATION COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN THE FIELD OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract: It is impossible to imagine without information and communication technologies in the field of preschool education and other fields of education. Information was given about the organization of the preschool education system based on the requirements of the present time, the formation of information and communication technologies in order to improve the quality of education in bringing the future generation to adulthood, making it healthy and mature in all respects. The general information about the connection of educational training of pedagogues and parents of preschool education organizations to the negative or positive aspects of young students in learning using information technologies in the future has been highlighted.

Keywords: information-communication and competence, child, education, games, modern technologies, multimedia, audio, video, animation programs, interactive lessons, interactive experience, interactive technologies.

INTRODUCTION

Forming the information and communication competence of students in the field of preschool education is one of the most important tasks that meets the requirements of today. This competence gives students the skills to express their

thoughts, communicate with other people, collect data, analyze and communicate accordingly.

As a result, students need to learn the most convenient ways to learn each information and communication skill, apply these skills in real life, and teach them to use them independently. In this case, it is necessary to teach students to express their thoughts directly, to communicate with people who take lessons from their thoughts. Thus, in order to develop the information and communication competence of students in the field of preschool education, it is necessary to teach them in practical ways, prepare meaningful lessons for them, interactive communication and information that includes human-related information. It is necessary to strive to apply curricula, creative approach and increase achievements in various fields and organize high-quality information and communication experience.

MAIN PART

There are many ways to allow formation of information and communication competence of students in the field of preschool education. By learning and practicing these techniques, students' skills can be developed. The formation and development of children's education from a young age is directly related to the environment in the family. The main activity of the child is games. Games are very important for the formation and development of a child's personality. In the information society, pedagogues of preschool education organizations have a number of tasks. First of all, the teacher should guide the child in choosing computer games and educational programs. For this reason, it is necessary for the educator to acquire computer literacy. It is important to be able to effectively and meaningfully use the resources of the global Internet network directly in the educational activities conducted with children of preschool age.

Use of computer games. Along with increasing the efficiency of the process of teaching the child, it gives a positive result in bringing out the creative and

intellectual potential of the child.

In the organization of interactive lessons, the most important thing in forming the information and communication competence of students is to organize meaningful lessons and interactive dialogues with teachers. Through this method, students improve their skills of expressing their thoughts, communicating with other people, gathering information and communicating accordingly. Pre-school educational institutions must be equipped in accordance with modern requirements. In the field of preschool education, computer games, interactive games necessary for students, for example, educational games, mathematics, teaching various languages, related to robotics games. Games that help to increase their interests are preferred. Games can increase children's motivation, provide an interesting and interactive method, strengthen cooperation between a child and a teacher, and facilitate the learning process. As a result, children will be able to feel that learning is more convenient and useful.

Interactive experience and interactive technologies in the field of preschool education are technologies that help students make the learning process more convenient and effective. Interactive technologies allow children to use more interactive methods of learning. These technologies help children to learn in a convenient and easy, interesting way.

In the field of preschool education, multimedia, audio and animation programs are one of the effective methods of working with children. Animation programs help to make the learning process interesting and interactive. Through animations, children have the opportunity to hide information, explain its details, or show problems visually. This program helps to make the learning process interesting when working with children, to develop relationships between children, and to increase the level of participation of children in the learning process.

CONCLUSION

The reason there is a big difference between the educator and the student in the field of preschool education in order to form the information and communication competence of students in the field of preschool education is that the educator has the ability to convey the understanding of information and communication to the child, first of all must have knowledge of the field. Based on the requirements of the present time, the educator should know how to create a dream in the child about what kind of field he would acquire in the future and achieve good results if he learns well and uses it in the right way. It is necessary to give understanding that it will lead to bad consequences. It is appropriate to use the telephone as an example. For their further development and improvement, students should apply and use their knowledge and skills in practical life. Information and communication competence can be needed by every student in different professions and life and is important for students to prove themselves effectively at higher levels in the future.

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7. O'quv dasturlar: Mazmunli o'quv dasturlari o'quvchilarni axborot-kommunikatsiya ko'nikmalarini o'rganish, ularni amaliy hayotda qo'llash va o'zlarini o'zlarining o'zini baholashga qaratadilar. O'quv dasturlarida interaktiv tajriba, testlar va amaliy mashqlar bo'ladi, bu axborot-kommunikatsiya ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratadi.
8. Inson bilan bog'liq ma'lumotlar: O'quvchilar boshqa insonlar bilan muloqot qilishni o'rganish uchun inson bilan bog'liq ma'lumotlardan foydalanishlari kerak. Bu ma'lumotlar jamiyatda mavjud bo'lishi mumkin, masalan, kelajakda ularga foydali bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan tadbirlarga qatnashish, soatlarining bir qismida o'quvchilarga o'zlarini mustaqil ravishda yondashuv va boshqa axborot-kommunikatsiya ko'nikmalarini o'rganish imkoniyatlarini beradi.